

Supporting Information

PbS/CdS Quantum Dot Room-Temperature Single-Emitter Spectroscopy Reaches the Telecom O and S Bands via an Engineered Stability

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Figure S1. (a) A PL intensity *versus* time trace for a single PbS/CdS nanocrystal over 6 hours at room temperature. The histogram of the emission intensity values is shown to the right of the trace, clearly displaying two-state behavior. (b) The PL intensity blinking from 0 to 200 seconds from (a). (c) Strong antibunching from a single nanocrystal with $g^{(2)}(0) \approx 0.4$ (acquired simultaneously with the intensity *vs.* time trace). The risetime in the coincidence counts is ~ 50 ns. This is significantly shorter than the microsecond photoluminescence lifetimes observed for the PbS/CdS QDs in general. We note that the ensemble lifetimes were obtained in solution, and it has been observed previously that the solid-state single-QD lifetime can be significantly shorter than the bulk lifetimes.¹ (d) and (e) An artificial 10 s bin time was applied to data from (a) to reveal that bright-dim fluctuations are indeed characteristic of both acquisition rates.

Discussion of bright/dim intensity fluctuations

We note here that blinking between bright and dim states, rather than bright and dark states, is similar to other QD systems for which blinking suppression has been demonstrated, *e.g.*, thick-shell CdSe/CdS QDs. When blinking is modified from bright/dark intermittency to bright/dim intermittency, it means that one of the mechanisms supporting blinking—non-radiative Auger recombination of charged states—has been suppressed.² In this case, charged-state emission is possible, though usually dim (but not always: Ref. 3) compared to excitonic emission.⁴ Thus, observation of fluctuation between bright and dim states in the case of PbS/CdS is consistent with the overall observation of shell-thickness-dependent blinking suppression, as Auger may also be suppressed in this system. This is particularly expected given that the PbS/CdS system can exhibit type II electronic behavior, like, *e.g.*, CdSe/CdS⁵ and InP/CdS⁶ that have also shown blinking suppression mediated by Auger suppression.

Figure S2. Size histograms for (a) PbS cores used to prepare (b), (c), (d) PbS/CdS QDs by sequential cation exchange, in order of increasing shell thickness and decreasing core size (Figure 2b, c, d, and Figure 4 QD1, QD2 and QD3 in main text, respectively).

Figure S3. PbS/CdS QD prepared by the partial cation exchange method were heated to two SILAR growth temperatures – 180 °C and 240 °C. The effect of temperature on QD spectral properties is shown in (a), where at the higher temperature, significant blue-shifting of the PL peak is observed. (b) and (c) show annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (ADF-STEM) images for the core/shell structures following exposure to the lower and higher SILAR temperatures, respectively. In both, overall particle shape and size is retained, but after exposure to the higher temperature, the PbS core is less apparent and, based on spectral blue-shifting, likely substantially smaller.

Figure S4. (a) Absorption spectrum expanded for PbS core (see Figure 2f black trace). (b) Absorption spectrum expanded for PbS/CdS core/thin-shell QD (see Figure 2f red trace).

Figure S5. Representative high-resolution TEM images of PbS/CdS QDs synthesized using the cation exchange shell growth method viewed in the [110] direction. These and other images were used to assess core size within the core/shell structures. Scale bars represent 2 nm.

Figure S6. Results of the time-resolved PL measurements for the PbS/CdS(~ 1.75 nm)/SILAR CdS(15 ML) core/shell structure. (a) 3D map of the time-resolved PL spectra. (b) The variation of the PL decay with the monitoring wavelength (indicated in the legend). (c) Variation in the average lifetime, $\langle \tau \rangle$, with the monitoring wavelength. The average lifetime was calculated according to Eq. 1 in the main text. The excitation wavelength was 404 nm. The instrument resolution is ~ 400 ps.

Figure S7. Structure of the electron and hole confinement potentials overlaid with the 1s electron (blue) and 1s hole (orange) density distributions for QD1–QD3 presented in Figure 4 illustrating the electron-hole localization regimes. Presented 1S electron and 1S hole energies do not include Coulomb binding energy. Adopted core diameters and shell radii were determined *via* TEM measurements and are listed in Table S1.

Table S1. Comparison of experimentally measured PL energies/wavelengths with calculated optical gaps (exciton energies) for QD1–QD3 as well as calculated electron-hole overlap integrals. The exciton energies include contributions from Coulomb interactions.

QD #	Total QD diameter	Core diameter	Shell thickness	Measured PL energy/wavelength	Calculated optical gap	Overlap integral
1	6.67 nm	4.8 nm	0.94 nm	0.91 eV / 1363 nm	0.93 eV / 1340 nm	0.97
2	6.49 nm	3.7 nm	1.40 nm	1.04 eV / 1192 nm	1.07 eV / 1145 nm	0.89
3	6.36 nm	2.6 nm	1.88 nm	1.27 eV / 976 nm	1.35 eV / 618 nm	0.72

Figure S8. S-band (PL ~ 0.8 eV; 1550 nm) PbS/CdS QDs exhibiting moderate (a) blinking suppression and (b) no photobleaching under 1 W/mm^2 excitation.

Figure S9. (a),(b) O-band and (c),(d) high-energy PbS/CdS QDs exhibiting strong excitation power dependencies for both blinking on-time fraction statistics and photobleaching trajectories. The average per-QD intensity is 2.75 and 2.84 times higher for excitation at 3.2 W/mm² compared to excitation at 1 W/mm², respectively, suggesting that we have not reached the saturation regime, as intensity increases approximately commensurate with power.

Figure S10. Intensity-time traces for single PbS/CdS core/shell QDs following SILAR shell growth interrogated using (a) 405 nm excitation (same QD as in Figure 5b,e, and h of main text) and (b), (c), (d) 840 nm excitation. For both excitations, the laser power was 3.2 W/mm². (b), (c), (d) are representative single QDs showing blinking behavior that is consistent with the range of behavior observed for these QDs, as shown in the blinking statistics in Figure 5e, where there is a large dispersity in on-time fraction. *E.g.*, (b) mostly fluctuates between on and dim states and would be emissive much of its intensity-time trajectory, while (c) fluctuates between on and dark or off states and would have a lower on-time fraction compared to (b). Comparing (b), (c), (d) with (a) here and with the on-time fraction analysis of Figure 5e in the main text shows that the two excitation wavelengths result in similar blinking behavior.

Figure S11. Linear fits of the dependence of the integrated PL intensity on the sample absorbance at the excitation wavelength for a representative PbS/CdS QD sample and IR26 dye.

Figure S12. Linear fits of the dependence of the integrated PL intensity on the sample absorbance at the excitation wavelength for a PbS/CdS QD sample and two reference QDs.

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